

Tarjimada kompensatsiya leksik transformatsiyasining ahamiyati*Masharipova Yulduz Otaxanovna**Urganch davlat universiteti tayanch doktoranti**E-mail: yulduz.m@urdu.uz**Tel: (93) 758 77 79*

Annotatsiya: Ma'lumki, tarjimada eng mos muqobilni topish juda muhim vazifalardan biri hisoblanadi. Tarjimon odatda asliyat tilidagi eng yaqin muqobilni tarjima qilinayotgan tilga moslashtirishga harakat qiladi. Bunda tarjimon leksik transformatsiya turi – kompensatsiyaning tarjimadagi ahamiyati, xususiyatlarini mukammal o'rgangan bo'lishi lozim. Chunki tarjimada kompensatsiyadan unumli foydalana bilishlik tarjimaning muvaffaqiyatli chiqishi garovidir.

Kalit so'zlar: kompensatsiya, stilistik usul, pragmatik ma'no, sinekdoha

Kompensatsiya leksik transformatsiyasi asliyat tilidagi u yoki bu birlikning tarjima tilida muqobili mavjud bo'lmaganida qo'llaniladi. Tarjimada asliyatdagi stilistik usullarning muqobili yoki ekvivalenti yo'q bo'lgan hollarda ham ushbu transformatsiya qo'llaniladi. Shuningdek, mazkur transformatsiyadan asar qahramonlarining nutq xususiyatlari, kamchiliklari, og'zaki nutqi, savodsizligi tufayli nutqda noto'g'ri so'zlarni qo'llashlari kabi holatlarni tarjima qilishda ham foydalaniladi. Asliyat matni pragmatik ma'nolarini yetkazishda ham kompensatsiya qo'llaniladi. Bunda asliyatdagi til birliklarining tarjima matnida kelish o'рни o'zgarishi mumkin. Mazkur transformatsiyaning yana bir o'ziga xos jihati shundaki, tarjima tili ekvivalentligi matnning alohida elementlari, xususan, so'zlar darajasida emas, balki butun bir matn ko'rinishida bo'lishi mumkin. [1; 37]

Mazkur risolada kompensatsiya leksik transformatsiyasi tahlili uchun misollar "O'tkan kunlar" romani va uning ingliz tiliga Kerol Yermakova, Mark Eduard Riz va I.M.To'xtasinovlar tomonidan qilingan tarjima variantlaridan olindi.

"O'tkan kunlar" romanidan olingan quyidagi parchada asliyat matni pragmatik ma'nolarini yetkazishda asliyat matni til birligining tarjima tilida muqobili mavjud

bo'Imaganda, tarjimada ushbu til birligining yo'qolib ketishini oldini olish maqsadida, uning o'rnini qoplash uchun tarjimonlar o'xshash variantlaridan qay darajada foydalanilganliklarini ko'rish mumkin: "Oftob oyim *"bachcha-machchadir"* deb o'ylag'an edi. Shuning uchun bu to'g'rida so'z ochmadi. - Tashqaridan xabar olingizchi, opa, - dedi Oftob oyim, - choy kerak bo'ldimikin. To'ybeka *nari-beri* oshini yeb tashqarig'a chiqib ketdi". [2; 32]

O'zbek tilining izohli lug'atida "bachcha" so'zi "odam bolasi; hayvon nasli" degan ma'nolarni anglatishi yozilgan bo'lib, uning quyidagi ma'nolari keltirilgan: 1. Bola. 2. Birovning (akavachchasining) qaramog'ida va ixtiyorida bo'lgan xushro'y, kelishgan o'yinchi o'g'il bola; besoqol. 3. Umuman o'yinchi bola, raqqos. [3; 182]

Asliyat matnida Otabekning Mirzakarim uyiga tashrifi tasvirlangan bo'lib, unda xonadon bekasi Oftob oyim va xizmatkori To'ybekaning suhbatini tasvirlangan. Bunda To'ybeka og'zidan tushirmay Otabekni maqtab kelganida, Oftob oyim uning maqtovlariga e'tibor bermay "bachcha-machchadir" deb o'ylab qo'ygani ifodalangan. Ya'ni, Oftob oyim tashrif buyuruvchi mehmonni, Otabekni, yosh bola deb o'ylagani aytilgan. Kerol Yermakova bu jumlaning "some bacha or other" (bacha yoki boshqa) deb [4; 35], Mark Eduard Riz esa "a Bacha" (bacha) deb [5; 52], I. M. To'xtasinov "some kind of adolescent" (qandaydir o'smir) deb tarjima qilishgan [6; 34]. Ko'rib turganingizdek, Kerol Yermakova va Mark Eduard Riz "bachcha" so'zini transliteratsiya qilish orqali berishgan bo'lishsa, I.M.To'xtasinov tarjimasida kompensatsiya kuzatilgan. Shuningdek, "nari-beri" jumlasining tarjima tili ekvivalentligi matnning alohida elementlari, xususan, so'zlar darajasida emas, balki izoh bilan berilgan. Ya'ni, asliyat tilidagi so'z tarjima tilida matn ko'rinishida kelgan. Bunda tarjimonlar asosan so'zning izohini keltirishgan. Shunday qilib, "nari-beri" jumlasini Kerol Yermakova tomonidan "hurriedly polished off" (shosha-pisha yeb tugatmoq) deb [4; 35], Mark Eduard Riz tomonidan "quickly swallowing" (tez yutish) deb [5; 52], I.M. To'xtasinov tomonidan esa "eating in haste" (shoshqaloqlik bilan ovqatlanish) deb tarjima qilingan [6; 34]. Shunday qilib, tarjimonlar kompensatsiyadan foydalangan holda o'zbek tili nutqi

madaniyatga oid, tarjimada muqobili mavjud bo'lmagan leksik birliklarning nomutanosibligining oldini olishga muvaffaq bo'lishgan.

Quyidagi aslyat matnida ma'nosi tarkibidagi so'zlarning leksik ma'nolari bilan bog'lanmaydigan, ular asosida izohlanmaydigan frazema "oyog'i olti, qo'li yeti bo'lib" frazeologik chatishmasi qo'llanilgan: "Zaynab oyog'i olti, qo'li yeti bo'lg'an holda erini to'rt qavat ko'rpacha ustiga o'tquzib, yoniga uchta par yostiqli uyd". [2; 350] O'zbek tilida "oyog'i olti, qo'li yeti bo'lib" frazemasini "shodlikdan o'zini hech qayerga sig'dirolmaydi, g'oyat xursand" degan ma'noni anglatadi. [7; 90] Ingliz tilida mazkur frazeologik chatishmaning muqobil varianti mavjud emasligi sababli, tarjimonlar uni tarjimada kompensatsiya orqali berishgan. Kerol Yermakova tarjimasida ushbu frazema alohida gap shaklida berilgan: "*Zainab strained every muscle trying to please her husband. She seated him on a thick blanket, folded in four, tucked three downy pillows by his side...*" [4; 309] Bunda "strained every muscle trying to please her husband" gapini o'zbek tilida "erini rozi qilishga jon jahdi bilan harakat qildi" deb tarjima qilinadi. Mark Eduard Riz bu iborani "overly obsequious" deb tarjima qilgan: "*Zainab, overly obsequious, had her husband sit upon a plush four-layered blanket and placed near him three down pillows for him to rest upon*". [5; 376] Bunda "overly obsequious" o'zbek tilida "juda ko'nglini olishga harakat qilmoq" deb tarjima qilinadi. I.M.To'xtasinov tarjimasida "beside herself with joy" (quvonchi ichiga sig'may) deb berilgan: "*Zainab beside herself with joy laid four layers of small quilts for him to sit on, putting three feather pillows beside*". [6; 340] Tarjima variantlari qiyosi natijasiga ko'ra I.M.To'xtasinov tarjimasida "quvonchi ichiga sig'may" ma'nosi aslyatdagi "g'oyat xursand" ma'nosiga muqobil variant bo'la olgan. Xulosa qilib aytganda, personajlar nutqi tasviri tarjima variantlarida namunali tiklanganini ko'rish mumkin. Ingliz tarjimonlari aslyatda personajlar nutqi tasviri aks etgan parchalarni o'z tillariga adabiy tarzda o'girganlar. Natijada aslyat bilan o'zbekcha tarjima orasida nomuvofiqlik yuzaga kelishini oldi olingan.

Ma'lumki, tarjimada stilistik vositalar kompensatsiya yordamida o'giriladi. "O'tkan kunlar" romanidan olingan quyidagi o'xshatishda Kumushning ahvoli

tasvirlangan: “Zaynab bu yolg‘onlash natijasidan qo‘rqib, o‘ngi ters ishiga yopishdi. Kumush *moddiy hayotidan ayrilg‘an jonivordek* bo‘shashdi”. [2; 349] Asliyat matnida Zaynab va Kumushning suhbat natijasida Kumushning Otabekni rashk qilgan holati “*moddiy holatidan ayrilg‘an jonivordek*” o‘xshatishi bilan ifodalangan. Kerol Yermakova tarjimasida bu o‘xshatish “*as though all her strength had seeped from her*” deb tarjima qilingan: “No sooner had her lie escaped her lips than Zainab took fright at the possible consequences, and quickly busied herself with her embroidery. But Kumush suddenly felt drained, as though all her strength had seeped from her”. [4; 309] O‘zbek tilida u “go‘yo butun kuchi yo‘qolib qolgandek”, “go‘yo bor kuchi undan chiqib ketgandek” degan ma‘noni bildiradi. Bunda faqat “kuchdan qolib, birdan bo‘shashib qolganlik” holati tasvirlangan, “jonivor”ga o‘xshatilishi berilmagan. Mark Eduard Riz tarjimasida bu o‘xshatish “surrendered to lassitude as if deprived of the will to live” deb berilgan: “Zainab, fearing the effects of her obfuscation, hid in her work, flustered and upset. Kumush surrendered to lassitude as if deprived of the will to live”. [5; 376] O‘zbek tilida u “yashash xohishidan mahrum bo‘lgandek mashaqqatga taslim bo‘ldi” degan ma‘noni bildiradi. Bu yerda ham faqat qanday tushkunlikka tushganlik holati ifoda etgan. I.M.To‘xtasinov tarjimasida “lost her heart” deb berilgan: “Zaynab got frightened of the result of this lie and started her work, turning it upside down. Kumush lost her heart”. [6; 340] O‘zbek tilida u “yuragini yo‘qotdi” degan ma‘noni anglatadi. Shunday qilib, tarjimonlar ushbu o‘xshatishni tarjimada kompensatsiya orqali berishgan deyish mumkin. Chunki, o‘zbek tiliga xos bo‘lgan mazkur o‘xshatishning ingliz tilida muqobil variant mavjud emas. Shuningdek, tarjimada uni asliyatdagidek berishning hech ham iloji yo‘q.

Keyingi misol ma‘no ko‘chish usulining bir turi – sinekdoha bilan bog‘liq. Sinekdoha – butun orqali qism, qism orqali butunni ifodalash asosida so‘zlardagi ma‘no ko‘chish usuli hisoblanadi. Masalan, “eshikka kirin mehmon bir chaqchaqlashamiz” bu gapda ma‘nosi ko‘chgan so‘z “eshik” so‘zi bo‘lib, bu gapda “eshikka kirin” deb “uy”ni nazarda tutmoqda. Quyidagi asliyat matnida ham sinekdoha qo‘llanilgan bo‘lib, unda “uyning oyog‘i” deganda “xonaning eshigi” nazarda tutilgan: “Bu hol bir daqiqa chamasi davom etkandan keyin biroz ajralishqan ko‘yi *uyning oyog‘ig‘a* yurib bordilar va tiza-

batiza o‘lturdilar ... [2; 332] Kerol Yermakova uni “the far end of the room” (xonaning eng chekkasi) deb tarjima qilgan: “They stood like this for a minute, then, pulling away from each other, went to the far end of the room and sat down”. [4; 294] Mark Eduard Riz uni “the end of the room” (xonaning oxiri) deb tarjima qilgan: “They stood there for some moments then pulled apart, walked to the end of the room and sat down, knees akimbo”. [5; 358] I.M.To‘xtasinov uni “the door side of the room” (xonaning eshik tomoni) deb tarjima qilgan: “They stood for a while, they parted and then they went to the door side of the room and sat on their knees ...” [6; 322] Shunday qilib, tarjima variantlarida “uyning oyog‘i” sinekdohasi turli xil shakllarda aniqlashtirib berilganini ko‘rish mumkin.

Quyidagi misol “tomoq” so‘zining tarjimasi bilan bog‘liq: “bu o‘rinda ikkisi ham jim bo‘ldilar. Oybodoq darichaga kelgan edi: “Tushlik osh vaqti bo‘ldimi, nima *tomoq* qilsamikin?” Kumush Zaynabka qaradi: - Nima *tomoq* buyuramiz?” [2; 347] O‘zbek tilida “tomoq” – “bo‘yinning engak osti qismi, bo‘g‘iz” degan ma‘noni bildiradi. Ko‘chma ma‘noda esa “taom, ovqat, ovqatlanish” degan ma‘noni anglatadi. [3; 144] Quyida “tomoq” so‘zining tarjima variantlarida qanday o‘zgarib ketganini ko‘rish mumkin. Kerol Yermakova tarjimasida “tomoq” so‘zi kompensatsiya orqali tarjima qilingan: “And the two of them fell silent. Aibadak glanced in through the window. “It’s lunchtime,” she called. “*What shall I cook for you?*” Kumush glanced at Zainab. “*What shall we order?*” she asked. [4; 307] Bunda “nima tomoq qilsamikin?” gapi tarjimada “What shall I cook for you?” (Sizlar uchun nima pishirsam ekan?) deb berilgan. “Tomoq” so‘zi tarjimada “cook” fe‘li bilan ifodalangan. Keyingi “Nima tomoq buyuramiz?” gapi tarjimada “What shall we order?” deb berilgan. O‘zbek tilida bu gap “Nima buyurtma beramiz?” deb tarjima qilinadi. Bunda ham “tomoq” so‘zi tarjimada “order” fe‘li bilan ifodalangan. Mark Eduard Riz esa “nima tomoq qilsamikin?” gapini quyidagicha tarjima qilgan: “Silence again rose between the two. Oibadak appeared in the small doorway. “It is lunchtime. *What should I prepare for you?*” Kumush looked at Zainab: “*What food should we order?*” [5; 373] Bunda “What should I prepare for you?” (Siz uchun nima tayyorlashim kerak?) deb tarjima qilgan. “Nima tomoq buyuramiz?” gapi esa “What food

should we order?” deb berilgan. Bunda “tomoq” so‘zi “food” deb tarjima qilingan. Ingliz tilida “food” so‘zi – “things that people or animals eat” (odamlar yoki hayvonlar yeydigan narsalar) degan ma‘noni anglatadi. Demak, bunda “food” so‘zi asliyatdagi “tomoq” so‘ziga muqobil variant bo‘la olgan. Endi I.M.To‘xtasinov tarjimasiga yuzlansak: “At this point they both kept silence. Oybodok approached the window and asked: “It seems time for lunch is coming, *what shall I prepare?*” Kumush looked at Zaynab: “*What shall we have?*” [6; 337] Tarjimaning bu variantidagi har ikkila gapda ham “tomoq” so‘zining ma‘nosi fe‘l bilan ifodalangan. Bunda birinchi gapda “prepare” fe‘li bilan kelgan bo‘lsa, ikkinchi gapda “have” bilan ifodalangan.

Navbatdagi asliyat matnida Zaynab bilan Kumushning suhbatini tasvirlangan: “Shunchalikka bir-biravimizdan chetlashib, *ming‘ayishib* yurishimiz kishiga og‘ir kelar ekan”. [5; 348] O‘zbek tilida “ming‘aymoq” fe‘li “qovoq-dimog‘ini solmoq, lab-lunjini osiltirmoq; araz qilmoq” degan ma‘nolarni bildiradi. [9; 598] Tarjima variantlariga yuzlanadigan bo‘lsak, unda Kerol Yermakova uni quyidagicha talqin etganini ko‘rish mumkin: “So why should we *sulk and quarrel with each other? That is not nice!*” [6; 307] Bunda “ming‘ayishib yurish” - “sulk and quarrel with each other” (bir-biri bilan janjallashish, so‘kish) deb berilgan. “Kishiga og‘ir kelar ekan” jumlasini “That is not nice” (Bu yaxshi emas) deb tarjima qilingan. Mark Eduard Riz tarjimasida ham kompensatsiyadan unumli foydalanilganini ko‘rish mumkin: “but all for the sake of a miserable misunderstanding, *we ignore each other. This hostility is hard to bear*”. [7; 374] Bunda “ming‘ayishib yurishimiz” jumlasini “we ignore each other” (biz bir-birimizni e‘tiborsiz qoldiramiz) deb berilgan. “*Kishiga og‘ir kelar ekan*” gapini “*This hostility is hard to bear*” (Bu dushmanlikka chidash qiyin) deb tarjima qilingan. I.M.To‘xtasinov tarjimasini: “It is a difficult situation when we avoid each other taking the sulks”. [8; 338] Bunda “we avoid each other taking the sulks” (biz bir-birimizdan xafalashib qochamiz) deb berilgan. Shunday qilib, tarjimaning har uchala variantida ham “ming‘ayishib” yurish holati alohida gaplar shaklida taqdim etilganini ko‘rish mumkin.

Navbatdagi asliyat matnida o‘zbek tili nutqiga xos bo‘lgan “voy o‘lay” jumlasini qo‘llanilgan: “Kumushning “uch-to‘rt kuni ...” bilan Zaynab yorishib ketgandek bo‘ldi:

“*Voy o‘lay*, Kumush opa, - dedi Zaynab bo‘shashqan ohangda, - chindan ham ko‘nglingizga olibsiz deyman. [5; 348] Kerol Yermakova “*voy o‘lay*” jumlasini “Don’t take on so” (bunday qabul qilmang) deb tarjima qilgan: “At the words ‘for some time’, Zainab’s face brightened. Her voice tender now, she said: “*Don’t take on so*, Kumush, my sister! You really took this too close to heart. [6; 307] Mark Eduard Riz “*voy o‘lay*” jumlasini “Oh, I should wither and die” (Oo, men qurib, o‘lishim kerak) deb tarjima qilgan: “Kumush’s statement that she had only intended to stay three or four days seemed to delight Zainab. “*Oh, I should wither and die*, sister Kumush,” said Zainab weakly. [7; 374] I.M.To‘xtasinov “*voy o‘lay*” jumlasini tarjimada tushirib qoldirgan va uni shunchaki “*Ah, my sister Kumush*” (Oo, Kumush singlim) gapi bilan bergan: “Hearing Kumush’s words “for a few days...” Zaynab seemed to get pleased: “*Ah, my sister Kumush*,” she said calmed down, “you seem to have been offended really. [8; 338]

Keyingi gap tarjimasi tarjimonlar uchun muammo bo‘lgani aniq bo‘lsa kerak: “*Ko‘nglimda tariqdek yomonlig‘im bo‘lsa*, ertagacha yetmayin”. [2; 348] O‘zbek tilida “tariq” so‘zi “boshhoqdoshlar oilasiga mansub bir yillik g‘alla o‘simligi va uning oqlab so‘k qilinadigan mayda doni” degan ma‘noni bildiradi. “Tariqday, tariqdek” deganda esa – “juda oz, jindak, kichkina, tariqcha” degan ma‘no tushuniladi. [3; 683] Demak, asliyat matnida “ko‘nglimda ozgina yomonlig‘im bo‘lsa” degan ma‘no anglashilgan. Kerol Yermakova uni quyidagicha tarjima qilgan: “May I not survive until tomorrow *if I have so much as a grain of ill-will in my heart!*” [4; 307] Bu gap o‘zbek tilida “yuragimda zarracha yomonlik bo‘lsa” deb tarjima qilinib, unda “a grain” so‘zi miqdorni anglatish maqsadida qo‘llanilgan. Ingliz tilida “a grain” quyidagi ma‘nolarni bildiradi: 1. The seeds from crops such as wheat, rice, or barley that are used for food (Oziq-ovqat uchun ishlatiladigan bug‘doy, guruch yoki arpa kabi ekinlarning urug‘lari). 2. A very small individual piece of a substance such as sand, salt, or sugar (Qum, tuz yoki shakar kabi moddaning juda kichik qismi) 3. An old unit for measuring weight, equal to 0.065 gram. (Og‘irlikni o‘lchash uchun eski birlik, 0,065 grammga teng). [8; 618] Demak, tarjimada “grain” so‘zining ikkinchi ma‘nosi ishlatilganini ko‘rish mumkin. Ya‘ni, u “biror narsaning juda kichik qismi” degan ma‘noda kelgan bo‘lib, bu miqdor “yurakdagi

yomonlik”ka nisbatan qo‘llanilgan. Shunday qilib, tarjimaning bu variantidan ma’lum bo‘ladiki, ingliz tilida ham “don” (grain) so‘zi biror narsaning miqdorini bildirishda qo‘llanilar ekan. Mark Eduard Riz tarjimasiga yuzlanadigan bo‘lsak, u bu gapni quyidagicha tarjima qilgan: “It seems to me that *you have taken all of my actions too much to heart* – I should die this very morning.” [5; 374] Bu gap o‘zbek tilida “siz mening barcha xatti-harakatlarimni yuragingizga juda yaqin olibsiz” degan ma’noni anglatadi. Tarjimaning bu variantida gapning ma’nosi kompensatsiya orqali gap strukturasi boshdan-oyoq qayta tuzish bilan o‘quvchiga tushunarli qilib yetirilgan. I.M.To‘xtasinov esa bunday tarjima qilgan: “*If I have something bad in my mind, let me die tomorrow*”. [6; 338] Bu gap o‘zbek tilida “Agar xayolimda yomon narsa bo‘lsa” degan ma’noni bildiradi. Shunday qilib, aslyat matnida kelgan o‘zbek tiliga xos bo‘lgan gap shakli tarjima variantlarida turlicha ko‘rinishlarda tarjima qilingan bo‘lishiga qramasdan, asosiysi tarjimada uning ma’no va mazmuni saqlanib qolganini ko‘rish mumkin.

Kompensatsiyaga misol bo‘luvchi so‘nggi matn tarkibida o‘xshatish qo‘llanilgan: “Yana ikki kundash *hujumga hozirlanishqan xo‘rozlardek* bir-birlarining ustlariga hurpayishdilar”. [2; 348] Mazkur aslyat matnida o‘zbek tilining stilistik vositalarga boyligiga yana bir bora amin bo‘lish mumkin. Bunda “kundosh”lar “hujumga hozirlangan xo‘rozlar”ga o‘xshatilgan. Kerol Yermakova tarjimasida bu o‘xshatish quyidagicha berilgan: “The rivals were once again sizing each other up *like two cocks preparing for a fight*”. [4; 308] Bunda “*like two cocks preparing for a fight*” – “jangga tayyorlanayotgan ikki xo‘roz kabi” degan ma’noni bildiradi. Tarjimaning bu variantida o‘xshatish kalkalash orqali berilganini ko‘rish mumkin. Mark Eduard Riz tarjimasida ham huddi Kerol Yermakovanikidek berilgan: “Again, the two kundosh strained toward each other *like two cocks preparing to fight*”. [5; 375] I.M.To‘xtasinov tarjimasida esa “*like cocks do*” deb tarjima qilingan: “Again two rivals went at each other *like cocks do*”. [6; 338] O‘zbek tilida “*like cocks do*” – “xo‘rozlar kabi” degan ma’noni bildiradi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, aslyatda tasvirlangan manzarani tillararo nomuvofiqliklar sababli har doim ham tarjima qilib bo‘lmasligi mumkin. Bunday vaziyatlarda tarjimonlar turli yo‘llar bilan o‘z personajlari holatini, nutqi davomida o‘zini qanday tutishini,

manzarani atroflicha tasvirlaydilarki, natijada tarjimada ularning tarjima tili lisoniy vositalari yordamida talqin etilishi sababligina pragmatik uyg'unlik yuzaga keladi. Tarjimaning bunday muammolari esa kompensatsiya yordamida yechim topadi.

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